

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		27-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Oosterhuis et al.	
Country of origin		The Netherlands	
Publication year		2017	
Title of article		Early rehabilitation after lumbar disc surgery is not effective or cost-effective compared to no referral: a randomised trial and economic evaluation	
Title of journal		Journal of PHYSIOTHERAPY	
Volume 63	Issue	Pages 144-153	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 145
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 145
Types of intervention		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 145
Types of comparison		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 145-146
Types of outcome measures		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 146
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>					

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	Research question: Is referral for early rehabilitation after lumbar disc surgery effective and cost-effective compared to no referral	p. 145
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	A multicentre, randomised, controlled trial	p. 145
Start date	May 2012	p. 147
End date	December 2014	p. 147
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear	Not reported

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Not reported	
Inclusion criteria	Eligible patients had a herniated lumbar disc confirmed by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and signs of nerve root compression corresponding to the level of disc herniation; were aged between 18 and 70 years; and were able to fill out questionnaires in Dutch themselves	p. 145
Exclusion criteria	If they met any of the following criteria: cauda equina syndrome, neurogenic claudication, co-morbidities of the lumbar spine (eg, fractures, carcinomas, osteoporosis), spinal surgery in the prior 12 months, contraindications to exercise therapy (eg, acute respiratory or cardiovascular complaints, acute systemic infections), pregnancy, or previous lumbar disc surgery at the same level and on the same side	p. 145
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	All participants gave written informed consent before data collection began p. 152

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Experimental group: referral for early rehabilitation	p. 145-150
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=92 (M:38, F:54) Mean age = 47	p. 148 table 1 p. 148 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Usual postoperative care and the following: Postoperative exercise therapy in primary care starting the first week after discharge. Over 6 to 8 weeks, participants received one or two individual, face-to-face, exercise therapy sessions of 30 minutes per week, conforming to a standardised treatment protocol based on a national clinical guideline. The 6- to 8-week period reflected the period before patients consulted their neurosurgeon again after surgery. In the first week, therapists performed physical examinations, and focused treatment on the ability and possibility to execute personal care activities and perform transfers in the home situation. From the second week onwards, exercises were taught with gradually increasing intensity, targeting limitations that were found in the initial postoperative assessment. The exact type of exercises was left to the therapists' discretion, based on the outcomes of the physical examination and taking participants' preferences into account, which was in line with routine clinical practice. Therapists provided tailored advice on lifestyle and the execution of activities of daily living. Treatment could be terminated before the end of the 6- to 8-week period if the participant was fully recovered.	p. 145

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group: no referral for early rehabilitation	p. 145-150
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=77 (M:33, F:44) Mean age = 47	p. 148 table 1 p. 148 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Usual postoperative care: During one or two sessions, a physiotherapist or nurse provided advice and instructions for transfers and performing activities of daily living, in preparation for discharge. At discharge, participants received a booklet providing advice (mainly regarding activities of daily living) and suggestions for exercises, focusing on muscle strengthening, core stability and mobilisation. After discharge from the hospital: Participants could consult their neurosurgeon or general practitioner in case of recurring or increasing complaints, but they were requested to refrain from referral for exercise therapy or other allied health interventions in the 6 to 8-week period before consulting the neurosurgeon after surgery.	p. 145-146

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Prognostic factors	p. 146
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Duration of symptoms and medication use preceding surgery, and complications during surgery Credibility/expectancy questionnaire, the Örebro Musculoskeletal Pain Screening Questionnaire, the Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire The Pain Coping Inventory	p. 146

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain (pain intensity leg, pain intensity back)	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	11 point Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) 0-10 No difference	p. 146

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Functional status	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) No difference	p. 146

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Global perceived effect	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	The seven-point Global Perceived Effect scale, ranging from 'completely recovered' to 'worse than ever'. This was dichotomised into success (completely and much recovered) and non-success (slightly recovered, no change, slightly worse, much worse and worse than ever).	p. 146

Outcome 5

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	General physical and mental health	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Medical Outcome Study Short Form 12 (SF-12) No difference	p. 146

Outcome 6

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Cost-effectiveness	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	EuroQol (EQ-5D-3L) Cost-effectiveness; incremental cost-effectiveness; quality adjustet life-years (QUALY's)	p. 146

Outcome 7

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Costs	p. 146
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	<p>Cost questionnaires</p> <p>A modified version of the Productivity and Disease Questionnaire was used to measure absence from paid work.</p> <p>Absenteeism costs were valued according to the friction cost approach using the estimated price of productivity losses per sickness absence day in the Netherlands based on 5-year age categories and gender.</p> <p>The friction cost approach assumes that costs are limited to the period needed to replace a sick worker (ie, the friction period, which is estimated to be 23 weeks in the Netherlands).</p> <p>Productivity losses from unpaid work (ie, all hours of volunteer work, and domestic and educational activities that participants were not able to perform due to their leg and back pain) were valued using a Dutch shadow price.</p>	p. 146

Follow up

Follow up	6 months (26 weeks)	p. 149 table 2, p. 150 table 3
-----------	---------------------	--------------------------------

Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Results: There were no clinically relevant or statistically significant overall mean differences between rehabilitation and control for any outcome adjusted for baseline characteristics: global perceived recovery (OR 1.0, 95% CI 0.6 to 1.7), functional status (MD 1.5, 95% CI -3.6 to 6.7), leg pain (MD 0.1, 95% CI -0.7 to 0.8), back pain (MD 0.3, 95% CI -0.3 to 0.9), physical health (MD -3.5, 95% CI -11.3 to 4.3), and mental health (MD -4.1, 95% CI -9.4 to 1.3). After 26 weeks, there were no significant differences in quality-adjusted life years (MD 0.01, 95% CI -0.02 to 0.04 points) and societal costs (MD -\$527, 95% CI -2846 to 1506). The maximum probability for the intervention to be cost-effective was 0.75 at a willingness-to-pay of \$32 000/quality-adjusted life year.</p> <p>Conclusion: Early rehabilitation after lumbar disc surgery was neither more effective nor more cost-effective than no referral.</p> <p>In conclusion, rehabilitation after lumbar disc surgery starting immediately after hospital discharge was neither effective nor cost-effective, compared to no referral for early rehabilitation.</p> <p>Participants in both groups improved more or less equally after surgery and early rehabilitation had no additional effect on pain, functional status, global perceived effect scale, general physical or mental health, or costs.</p>	<p>Abstract</p> <p>p. 152</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>